

DATABASE ACQUISITION

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The number of hotels in our region in 2017-2022 increased by 4 times, the number of tourist restaurants, guides, tour operators increased by 4.5 times, the number of visiting tourists increased by 5 times, and the number of tourist buses and minibuses increased by 10 times.

As a result of the implementation of decrees and decisions and the conducted propaganda, the number of tourists who came to Bukhara in 2021 was 2 million 265 thousand, and in the eight months of 2022 this figure exceeded 2 million 313 thousand. The number of local tourists - 2 million 216.5 thousand in 2021, 2 million 12.3 thousand in eight months of 2022; The number of foreign tourists was 49,000 in 2021, and increased to 363,000 in eight months of 2022.

Employment of means of placement in the region in 2021 was 32.6%, in September 2022, this indicator shows that it has exceeded up to 90%.

Uzbekistan has long been considered a country with great tourist potential. The resources of educational tourism are very large. The country has about 7,000 International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. FARS Publishers Impact factor (SJIF) = 6.786 Publishing centre of Finland 557 historical and cultural monuments, medieval mosques and madrasas, grandiose architecture of the Tamerlane era. Uzbekistan impresses with its mountain landscape, desert and lakes! The nature of Uzbekistan surprises with incomparable landscapes and gives room for the formation of various options for active tours. The main tourist cities of the country are Bukhara, Samarkand, Khiva, and Tashkent, known since the time of the Great Silk Road (Kamalova S., 2019).

Analysis of our surveys among tourists shows that 1 out of 7 of them expressed a desire to return to Uzbekistan again.

Currently, inbound tourism in Uzbekistan is going through difficult times, primarily due to the recent pandemic situation. Recently, the main direction of state support has been the development of inbound and domestic tourism. Although recently there have been positive developments in the development of domestic tourism and attracting foreign visitors.

References:

1. Sh. Juraeva, Tourism and hospitality market database: gathering and updating the information.